

Colibrys sensors: output voltage

1. Goal

Colibrys documentation points out the need of a low pass filter on output voltage (V_{out}):

COLIBRYS PRODUCT ELECTRICAL INTEGRATION IN SYSTEM

Why a low pass filter on V_{out} ?
Switched capacitors introduce spikes on output voltage as presented on the next graph:

No spikes using VS1000.A

Temperature sensor is LM20 and manufacturer preconizes applying one low pass filter to reduce noise on V_o .

A Low Pass Filter was implemented with a resistor and a capacitor, with bandwidth around 270 Hz. The components were soldered directly on the board, as it can be seen on following picture:

Goal of the test is to demonstrate the effect of the low pass filter and compare the two measurements: with and without filter.

2. Setup

- Colibrys on Evolution Board (with and without LPF)
- Battery as Power Supply: 4.73V
- Oscilloscope

Pin assignment Colibrys:

- Blue = GND
- Red = VCC
- Yellow = Vout (Sensor's output signal)

Pin assignment Battery:

- Black = GND
- Red = VCC

3. Data Analysis

- Files Location: SVN\spark_sling_load\trunk\09_Sensors\Colibrys\Test Vout LPF
- Procedure:
 - o Measurement acquisition time: +/- 250 ms
 - o Csv File generated from oscilloscope and copied to computer
 - o Import Csv File in Matlab
 - o Plot Data

4. Outcome

